

Role of Emotion and Behaviour in Marketing

* Himanshu Agarwal

Abstract- *For several decades, marketers have been tirelessly searching for a highly coveted but apparently elusive prize: Customer Satisfaction. The problem is they have been pursuing the wrong goal. Regardless of how high a company's customer satisfaction levels may appear to be, satisfying customers without creating an emotional connection with them has no real value. In today's scenario a new light on what actually required for a truly connected and valuable is customer relationship. Emotional Marketing being the new paradigm for connecting to customers presents a deep resonance with the consumer needs and leaves a long-lasting impression leading to loyalty. This paper explores the effectiveness of Emotional Marketing and winning the customers for life through this approach.*

Key Words: *Emotional Marketing, Consumer Satisfaction, Limbic Brain, Reconnecting with consumers, Unconscious Processing*

Introduction- It has become a set formula in the present day strategic - marketing - scenario that to make a customer brand loyal forever - deal him emotionally irrespective of the nature of the business. Consumer behavior has now become the established science today. And, a person when wishes to buy something, proceeds in a defined manner and goes through a standard course of action. This is a process of assessing and analyzing the various options available while examining the worth of the product and its suitability as a whole. Finally, when he decides to purchase the product, nothing can prevent him from making the purchase. The emotional desire is matter of unique personality that builds desire and action that compel purchase decision. This is what emotional marketing strive for, and the successful product brand achieves this for happiness of the consumers and the profitability of the company. Be it Titan, LIC, Nestle, AXE, Red & White cigarette, Vimal or any other else they have all been successful in tapping the emotions of individuals. Of course, basing upon the emotions only will do no good unless the consumer enjoys the utility factor clubbed with the same. It is then smartness of the company to think of the right amount of emotional component in promoting the brand and making it successful in this highly competitive world. Be it a fabric for an important occasion or jewelry or a four wheeler for that matter, the emotional component in marketing will certainly make a lot of difference.

Emotional Marketing: Meaning- What the Mobile Telphony Company IDEA

* Reader, Faculty of Commerce and Busi. Admn., D N College, Meerut

is doing? It is just emotionally and ethically diverting customer-base towards mobile use. Every company claims to be the best, the least expensive, the most desirable. How does one promote the value of the product/service in a way that convinces the target market that you're the obvious choice? While the competitors are busy pumping out boring and rational, or, over-the-top self-focused marketing, one can be touching one's prospects where it counts. When people realize (and that realization can happen in a fraction of a second) that you "get it" about their pain or passion, you've created an emotional connection that goes beyond mere words. Emotional marketing is the kind of marketing that the big marketing companies have used for ages. It was born from their research into the human psychology of what causes us to buy things. Think about that for a moment. When you make purchases, why do you make them? Think about the process involved and the differences between things you planned to buy, and those that you did not plan on buying but did anyway. We would bet in each case that there was some kind of emotion that pushed you to pulling out your wallet, checkbook, or credit card wasn't there? We are sure that after the purchase you had all kinds of reasons to logically back up your purchase didn't you? But if you take all of that logic away, and dig deeper into the principles that actually motivated you to make the purchase, then we will bet that the underlying reason was the way that the purchased item made you feel. It is okay. You are not alone. You are no different than us or anyone else who buys things. We all buy based on the way that a product or service makes us feel, and the big marketing companies all know that. It's all about perception and how your products/services make a potential buyer feel.

Marketing Effort Emotions-

1. **Achievement** - How does your product/service contribute to the customer's achievement or accomplishment of something notable in life? In this example, your product/service becomes part of the customer's identity. For example, the advertisements of edible oils and Kurkure, Chocolate and Chocó.
2. **Pride of Ownership** - How does your product/service contribute to the pride someone would feel from ownership? When you pit pride against features or benefits, pride usually wins in the end. For example, the Rupa undergarment.
3. **Security** - What kind of security does your product/service offer? This is a blanket emotion that includes money, love, acceptance, power and control. Do not emphasize it if you cannot offer it. For example, the advertisement of Halls.
4. **Self-improvement** - How does your product/service appeal to a person's self improvement needs? The internet was born from information relay ideas. Almost everyone uses self-improvement books, articles, or newsletters of some kind. Information is what keeps the internet moving, and content is

king. For example, the advertisement of soaps.

5. Status - How does your product/service contribute to the status your visitor achieves? Everyone knows that you can fly in second class because it is cheaper and more economical, but deep inside almost everyone would rather fly in first class. What is the "first class" of your product or service? For example, the advertisement of RIN.
6. Style - How does your product/service fit your buyer's style? Are your products/services the Cadillac of style, or are they the Hugo? Keep in mind that their style needs can be real or imagined. For example, the advertisement of small cars.
7. Conformity - Does your product/service fall into a conformity niche? People do not want to be alone. They flock together in groups. You have seen them throughout school, and surely have seen them in your adult life. Does your product or service command over this type of emotion? For example, the advertisement of PanParag.
8. Ambition: Human beings always cherish adding more value to life. For example, the Lipton Tea advertisement of Soaps.

Targeting Emotions- Reasons- It is not required here to mention the basic common goal of the company. Every Company wants to increase the size of earning, multiply the coverage and to set its monopoly. These mentioned points are the simple reasons for targeting emotions.

- Focus on attention: The experts say that emotion acts as the warning system for the rest of the brain. This role is rooted in the evolutionary development of the brain and is linked to survival. Emotion sends a message to the brain to pay attention. Therefore, the best way to get someone's attention is to stimulate strong emotional responses.
- Major determinant to remembrance: Although facts and other information are stored in memories, the experiences that generate the strongest emotions are the ones that are stored most easily and most clearly for many years.
- Essential Ingredient in the Development of Attitudes: Attitudes are facts linked with emotion. Attitudes, in turn, influence one's choices, decisions, and behavior on an ongoing basis.
- Emotions are the basis of motivation: Goleman points out that the words emotion and motivation both come from the same Latin root verb meaning 'to move. In order to motivate someone one must move them emotionally. And motivation most often produces action or movement.

Consumer Buying Behavior and the Working of Brain- The link between emotion and behavior is a more strong association than that of thought and behavior. Darwin described how a person observing a mad dog take a safe position behind the table would jump back if the dog suddenly comes toward the table. The puzzling question that arises is, why someone would jump for safety if he knows he was

already safe. It turns out that our brains are wired to take a short cut. The short cut connects directly to the motor neurons initiating behavior. Importantly, the shortcut is stimulated by emotion. In the presence of strong emotion, a physical reaction occurs before understanding and comprehension. Therefore, emotion focuses attention, determines what is remembered, shapes attitudes, motivates, and moves one to act. It should not come as a surprise that the emotional centers of the brain have become the primary target for marketers and advertisers. This list of roles that emotions play could easily be mistaken for an advertiser's wish list.

The brain of the baby who comes into the world consists of 100 billion neurons and the possible dendrite connections are trillion. It is estimated that about 17% of the wiring is completed at the time of birth. For the years to follow, the neural framework of the brain is formed by connecting billions of neurons with one another. The two forces which help in the wiring of the growing human brain are genetics and experience. The arrangement of neurons by DNA is hard wiring and the networks which are shaped by experience are soft wiring.

A baby's brain is a mystery whose secrets scientists are just beginning to unravel. The mystery begins in the womb-only four weeks into gestation, the first brain cells, the neurons, are already forming at an astonishing rate of 250,000 per minute. Billions of neurons forge links with billions of other neurons, and eventually, there will be trillions and trillions of connections between cells. Every cell is precisely in its place, every link between neurons carefully organized. Nothing is random, nothing is arbitrary. The debate over whether nature or nurture is responsible for the wiring is fading. The wiring of a child's brain is shaped by the constant interplay between nature and nurture. Although some of the wiring is genetically determined, experience clearly plays a major role in building the brain that will eventually drive the vast array of mental capabilities.

While the many components of the brain operate together in a coordinated manner, it is often helpful to examine the major brain systems separately. Daniel Coleman notes three main brain systems: the brainstem, the limbic system, and the cortex. The brainstem governs physiological functions like temperature regulation and heart rate- functions necessary for survival. The limbic system is the primary system of emotion, attention and memory. It is also the location of the emotional brain, i.e., it governs the state of our emotions. The third brain system, the cortex, governs the 'higher order' brain functions such as language, pattern recognition, and reasoning. All functions of the brain are important. However, it is useful to consider the role of the limbic brain, or emotion, in the workings of the mind. Advertisers aim for the emotional centers of the brain. If that is the case, then one needs to keep in mind the critical roles that emotions play to understand the effectiveness of media in influencing people.

Advertising and the Limbic Brain: It has become clear that all emotions, attentions and memory are called limbic Brain. Thus, advertising messages are

aimed at the limbic brain and can stimulate emotional reactions. These feelings are further linked to the perception of the product. This is how emotional reactions begin to influence attitudes and values. An emotional response affects the attitude about the product being sold before the cortex brain (The Higher Reasoning Brain) even knows what is being sold.

Understanding this process can help explain a consistent finding in the literature-that people assume other people are more influenced by the media than they are themselves. This tendency has been called the third person effect and can be easily demonstrated if one is in a large group of people. Simply ask people to raise their hands if they think that advertisements affect people a lot and most of the hands will go up. Then ask them to raise their hands if they think that advertisements affect themselves a lot, and most of the hands will go back down. This belief that ads 'do not affect me' can make one wonder whether advertising matters. However, advertisements are constructed to have exactly this effect- to influence people without their being conscious or aware of having been influenced. Because emotional responses do not engage reason, they can easily slip in undetected under the radar of critical judgment. Then they subtly but powerfully begin to shape the way the product is viewed without a conscious awareness of the process. The art of advertising is difficult to master and it takes a great deal of skill and creativity to achieve proficiency. However, the underlying psychological principles are quite simple. The most effective advertisements create an emotional state. Once the desired state is achieved the product or message is then linked to the state. Sometimes, the examples of this are quite clear. Viewers seeing a television ad for the first time may not know what the product is, until the very last seconds of the ad. The reason is that the first 28 seconds of the 30-second ad are used to create the mood. Once the mood is set, the product is introduced and the emotional association is made. A synaptic bridge in the brain has been constructed.

Advertisement: Informational Vs. Emotional- In my opinion, all advertisements, whether they are visual, verbal or print, are more or less based on emotional backgrounds. We have only two divides of the society viz. man and woman. Most of the advertisement either arouses masculine emotions or feminine emotions. Sometimes sexual attraction phenomenon is used to intensify sale. As long as the desired emotion is linked with the product, the mission has been pushed. It has been accomplished because of the critical roles, discussed earlier; that emotion plays in the workings of the brain: attention, memory, attitudes, motivation, and behavior. While discussing the Hallmark's Value Star Robinette et al. (2004) describe how emotion plays a powerful role in a consumer's perception of value and in driving long-term loyalty. This motivational framework or Value Star has with five factors, viz. money, product, equity, experience, and energy. The Value Star makes an important distinction between the rational components (Money, Product) and the emotional components (Energy, Equity, and Experience). The

distinction is about answering the questions: 1. what do people need? 2. What moves them to act and advocate that the emotional components but also drive the majority of the decisions to purchase.

Hallmark's Value Star

Source: *Hallmark's Value Star, Robinette et. Al (2004)*

Emotional Marketing in India- Dozens of insurance players have recently entered the market. If the reasons are explored, it will be observed that they are simple. They have understood the untapped market in India and the other is the surety of business in an emotionally-driven market in the insurance sector. Various industries have been liberalized since the last decade, but what has made it extremely attractive for the foreign players and many more Indian corporate giants to explore the insurance sector is the surety in tapping the emotions of Indians. Many striking examples could be quoted to explain the emotional appeal used in the marketing of products and services. Titan has made the use of strong emotional appeal in most of its ads wherein the watches match the personalities of individuals.

- Baja has also made use of the emotional appeal and this is obvious from its tag line "HAMARA BAJAJ".
- Hero Honda says that this is DESH KI DHARKAN "DHAK DHAK".
- Tata Namak questions of your patriotism DESK KANAMAK KHAYA KYA?
- Hero Honda Pleasure one of Hero Honda's bikes for girls raises the girls' inner desire of feel like a boy and says "WHY SHOULD BOYS HAVE ALL THE FUN?"
- HDFC Life Insurance says the every retired person to live with their self-respect and says "SIR UTHHA KE JIYO".
- Vodafone is "HAPPY TO HELP".
- "AXE EFFECT"
- We all are of worried about phone balance while our dear ones are far from us, here is the solution provided by Airtel which says "AB KOI DURIYA NAHIN".

This is only a small glimpse of Indian Industry the rest is remaining and will

take a full book to explain as Indians are known as emotional beings rather than rational that's why every company whether Indian or Multinational plays with these emotions for increasing their market share and brand loyalty. In order to earn loyalty of customers, company has to gain the trust of its customers. And this can be done only by providing the customers with those what they want or need from the product and making them aware of that they can complete their needs with company's product. And this can be done only through connecting with emotions of customers. For several decades, marketers have been tirelessly searching for a highly coveted but apparently elusive prize: customer satisfaction. The problem is, they've been pursuing the wrong goal.

That's right. Regardless of how high a company's customer satisfaction levels may appear to be, satisfying customers without creating an emotional connection with them has no real value. In today's scenario a new light on what is actually required for a truly connected-and valuable is customer relationship.

Myths and Clearances- Some analysts have cast doubt on the widely held belief that loyalty translates to profitability. Their findings stem from confusion regarding how loyalty should be identified and measured. In several cases, "loyalty" has been defined by customer behavior, and repeated purchase has been considered evidence of a customer's loyalty. But this type of customer loyalty may not be profitable. That's because repeated purchase behavior has been motivated-or bribed-by a company's offers of gifts, discounts, or other purchase. These customers aren't really loyal; they're just customers who haven't left-yet.

Behavioral measures of loyalty are often misleading because they can't differentiate between customers with brand allegiance and those with no commitment. The uncommitted may appear to be loyal, but they only remain customers out of habit or because the company continues to bribe them. They're susceptible to the incentives and discounts competitors will offer to induce them to switch. But who are a company's truly loyal customers? To find out, companies need measures that extend beyond behavior-based indices. As Werner Reinart and V. Kumar noted in a Harvard Business Review article, "To identify the true apostles, companies need to judge customers by more than just their actions." Others echo their sentiments. Wharton's Peter Fader states, "It is hard to diagnose past behavior to understand why people did what they did. Historical behavioral data is rich and interesting, but it has its limits as a guide to the future."

Customer satisfaction assessment was heralded some time ago as the obvious solution to the need for more meaningful customer measures. Satisfaction, it was claimed, provides insight into the reasons why customers behave as they do and is not merely a reflection of repeated behavior that may have been earned - or "purchased"-by the company. But we have learned, as Thomas Jones and Earl Sasser Jr. observed in a 1995 Harvard Business Review article, "satisfied customers defect." Of course they do, and that's why so many companies have adjusted their

satisfaction standards to correspond with the recommendations in that famous article. Companies are now setting higher goals, aiming at "complete" customer satisfaction, and using extreme agreement ratings to gauge not just basic satisfaction but genuine customer "delight." Taylor and LaBarre offer five principles to consider in reconnecting with customers.

1. There's always a demand for something distinctive.
2. Not all customers are created equal.
3. Brand is culture, culture is brand.
4. Advertising to customers is not the same as connecting with customers.
5. When it comes to creating brand value, dollars-and-cents thinking doesn't always make sense.

Conclusion- The aforesaid brain, emotion, behavior and Marketing discussion crystal clears that the emotional marketing is not bad in any way for a company who wants to sell its products and to further diversify. The company's motive is targeted. And, as we know that thousand of emotions die under the curtains of the heart. Being emotional or arousing one's emotion is bad where we are misusing or selling inferior quality goods. Yes! In this emotional drive it may possible that we can purchase such things we never require or we may purchase that quantity we don't need anyhow. Emotion stimulates the mind 3000 times faster than rational thought. It's an emotional world we live in. Many people say we live in a rational world but nothing could be further from the truth. Emotions drive our behavior; the world is driven by emotions. Rational thought leads customers to be interested but it is emotion that sells. People really aren't much interested in attributes; they want to know if they can have a product that suits their personality. It is all about values. Therefore, in this world of competition and consumerism, every company will boost product line for a high graph of sale. If we will not try this aspect some others well do this. So, emotional sales drives are not bad if the product being provided to the customer are qualitative, value for the money and guarded by Guarantee or warranty.

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